

THE EFFECT OF THERMO-OXIDATION ON MATRIX CRACKING OF CROSS-PLY [0/90]_s COMPOSITE LAMINATES

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Keywords: *thermo-oxidation, matrix cracking, cross-ply sample*

1 General Introduction

Composite materials have been increasingly integrated within aerospace structures as they possess very interesting specific mechanical properties (strength and stiffness) and very good fatigue resistance. In the next future composite materials are expected to be employed in structural parts subjected to rather severe thermal conditions. For instance, composite structures for aero – engines can be exposed to oxidative environments at high temperatures (>120°C); under such conditions oxidation reaction/diffusion phenomena take place within the polymer material and threaten the integrity of the structure.

Thermo-oxidation of organic matrix composites has been the subject of specific studies over the past ten years [1-4]: the coupled oxygen diffusion/reaction phenomenon leads, on one hand, to matrix chemical shrinkage strains due to the departure of volatile species and, on the other hand, to the formation of an oxidized layer in which the mechanical properties of the material are degraded. Chemical shrinkage sums up to existent hydro, thermal, mechanical strains and can contribute significantly to the development of internal stresses. At the microscopic scale (the scale of the fibre), the stress concentration existing close to the fiber-matrix interface can induce microscopic damage, such as fiber-matrix debonding. At the lamina/laminate scale, internal and applied stresses may give rise to damage under the form of matrix cracking and delamination: the development of such damage can be affected by thermo-oxidation; moreover the interaction between

damage and oxygen diffusion can then accelerate the kinetics of degradation and affect the durability of the laminate.

In this article the effects of thermo-oxidation on matrix cracking of cross-ply [0/90₃/0] IM7/977-2 composite specimens (size: 180 mm x 20 mm x 1.25 mm) were investigated. Samples were first subjected to isothermal aging tests at 150°C under 1.7 bar of oxygen and then to quasi-static tensile tests up to rupture. The sample polished edges were observed at regular intervals during the tensile test by a traveling optical microscope mounted on the tensile machine in order to count the number of matrix transverse cracks appearing in the 90° layers.

Replicas of the sample surface edges were also observed by Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) to establish a possible link between thermo-oxidation damage at the microscopic scale (fiber-matrix debonding) and the onset of transverse matrix cracks in the 90° layers.

2 Experimental setup

2.1 Sample preparation

The samples (dimensions: 180 mm x 20 mm x 1.25 mm) were cut out from a [0/90₃/0] IM7/977-2 composite plate and polished automatically by an optimized procedure, set up to minimize the impact of polishing (see Fig. 1). The material elastic properties of the unidirectional laminate are given in Tab. 1. The samples were then subjected to isothermal aging tests at 150°C under 1.7 bars oxygen pressure in a climatic chamber [3] before undergoing quasi-static tensile tests.

Fig. 1: Sample geometry and dimensions.

Properties	20°C
E_{11}	157 GPa
E_{22}	8,5 GPa
ν_{12}	0,29
G_{12}	5 GPa
α_1	$0,23 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$
α_2	$30 \times 10^{-6} \text{ } ^\circ\text{C}$

Tab. 1. Properties of unidirectional laminate.

2.2 Testing machine

Tensile tests were carried out on a hydraulic Instron 4505 machine (maximal load 100 kN).

Fig. 2: "In situ" observation setup for crack counting during tensile test.

In situ observations of polished samples edges were performed during the tensile test without dismounting the sample by means of a video camera and a long distance Questar microscope (Fig. 2). The camera transfers the images to a computer screen and transverse cracks can be counted at each stage of the loading.

3 Numerical simulation of matrix cracking in $[0/90]_s$ cross-ply composite laminate under static tensile test

Matrix cracking in off-axis plies is usually the first type of damage appearing in composite laminates. A lot of experimental work has been carried out on $[0/90]_s$ cross-ply laminates in order to identify and characterize the physical and geometrical parameters governing the onset, propagation and saturation of

matrix cracks under mechanical or thermal loading. Based on the experimental results, researchers have proposed models to predict these phenomena. The mechanical analysis of damage evolution in the composite consists of two main steps:

- The first step aims at describing the stress field in the $[0/90]_s$ laminate in the presence of damage.
- The second step involves using a failure criterion to predict damage evolution.

In the literature, different methods for calculating the stress field in $[0/90]_s$ cross-ply laminates have been presented. Among them, the "shear-lag" model is one of the most used. Nairn and Mendels [5] have recently classified the "shear-lag"-based models by developing elastic calculations of general multi-layer systems in which matrix cracking in $[0/90]_s$ cross-ply laminates is a particular case. The authors show that, whatever the stress distributions along the thickness, all the approaches lead to a fundamental "shear-lag" equation:

$$\frac{d^2 \tau_{xz}^*(x)}{dx^2} - \alpha^2 \tau_{xz}^*(x) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$-L \leq x \leq +L$ (Fig. 3); $\tau_{xz}^*(x)$ is shear stress at layers interface; « α » is a « shear-lag » parameter:

$$\alpha^2 = \left[\frac{1}{h_1 E_{22}} + \frac{1}{h_2 E_{11}} \right] \left[\frac{h_1 k_R}{G_{23}} + \frac{h_2 k_L}{G_{13}} \right] \quad (2)$$

E_{11} , E_{22} , G_{23} and G_{13} are the elastic mechanical properties of the unidirectional laminate; k_R and k_L are constants which depend on the distribution of shear stress τ_{xz} along the thickness.

For a material similar to ours, by using $k_R=0.3300$ and $k_L=0.3070$, Nairn and Mendels [5] showed that the stresses calculated by "shear-lag" models are very close to finite element results. Using an approach proposed by Lee and Daniel [6], Berthelot et al. [7] found a good agreement with the finite element calculations for $k_R=1/3$ and $k_L=1/3$. The study by Nairn and Mendels shows the high efficiency and simplicity of "shear-lag" models.

In the present paper, we will take $k_R=1/3$ and $k_L=1/3$ to calculate the stress field.

A failure criterion is necessary to predict damage evolution. In this study, we employ an energetic approach: we assume that a crack forms when the energy release rate due to the creation of new crack

exceeds the critical energy release rate of the laminate. The crack appears on the edge of the specimen and propagates instantaneously across the entire thickness and width. The study is limited to the elastic case but taking into account the influence of thermal stresses on the calculation of the energy release rate. The general procedure for the calculation of the energy release rate of composite systems has been presented by Nairn [8]. We apply these results to an elementary cell between two matrix cracks, obtaining an expression for the energy release rate due to the onset of a new crack between two existing cracks (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Appearance of a new crack between two existing cracks.

Within the elementary cell (Fig. 3), the energy release rate can be calculated using two different definitions. The first uses the concept of discrete fracture mechanics [9] and calculates the energy release rate, G , through the expression:

$$G = -\frac{\Delta E_p}{\Delta A} \quad (3)$$

E_p is the potential energy; ΔA is the discrete variation of damaged area (the area of a new crack). In this case, the expression of energy release rate associated with the apparition of new crack in the middle of two existing cracks can be written as:

$$G(\bar{\sigma}, d) = G_{\max}(\bar{\sigma}) \times f_d(d) \quad (4)$$

With:

$$G_{\max}(\bar{\sigma}) = \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{E_{22}}{E_x} \frac{1}{E_{11}} (1+h_{12})^* \quad (5)$$

$$\left[\bar{\sigma} - \frac{1}{1+h_{12}} E_{11} \Delta \alpha_{21} \Delta T \right]^2$$

$$f_d(d) = 2 \tanh\left(\frac{\alpha}{4d}\right) - \tanh\left(\frac{\alpha}{2d}\right) \quad (6)$$

α is calculated by ((1); $E_x = \frac{E_{11} + h_{12} E_{22}}{1 + h_{12}}$,

$h_{12} = \frac{h_1}{h_2}$; $\Delta \alpha_{21} = \alpha_2 - \alpha_1$ and $d = 1/(2L)$ is the

crack density.

The second definition uses the notions of classical fracture mechanics, for which the expression of the energy release rate associated with the appearance of a new crack between two existing cracks is:

$$G = -\frac{\partial}{\partial A} [E_p] \quad (7)$$

Eq. (7) gives an expression which is similar to Eq. (4) with a different $f_d(d)$:

$$f_d(d) = \tanh\left(\frac{\alpha}{2d}\right) - \frac{\alpha}{2d} \left[1 - \tanh^2\left(\frac{\alpha}{2d}\right) \right] \quad (8)$$

This last expression is employed in our study.

4 Results and discussions

4.1 Evaluation of critical energy release rate

Fig. 4 shows the evolution of matrix crack density as a function of the applied stress measured on four different samples: un-aged, pre-aged at 150°C under 1.7 bars oxygen for 24h, 48h and 96h, respectively. Two test series were carried out to ensure the reproducibility of the experimental results. It is noted that there is a clear gap between the curve of the un-aged samples and the curves of pre-aged samples (Fig. 4). For a given applied stress, the pre-aged specimens have a higher crack density (ex 25% for an applied stress of 600MPa) compared to un-aged specimens. However, it is shown that the cracking kinetics are similar for all the pre-aged samples (24h, 48h and 96h). We deduce that the pre-aged samples have all the same matrix cracking behaviour, in spite of their different aging time.

Fig. 4: Evolution of matrix crack density as a function of the applied stress in [0/90₃/0] laminates: un-aged (0h), pre-aged under 1.7 bars oxygen at 150°C (24h, 48h and 96h) samples.

From these experimental data, the critical energy release rate, G_c , of the samples can be evaluated using a failure criterion of the type $G = G_c$. Fig. 5 shows the results of numerical calculations carried out with different values of G_c (assumed constant with crack density) and a comparison with the experimental results.

Fig. 5: Experimental – numerical evolution of matrix crack density as a function of the applied stress (G_c taken constant with crack density)

We identify a value of $G_c = 480$ (J/m^2) for un-aged specimens and $G_c = 350$ (J/m^2) for pre-aged (24h, 48h, 96h) specimens. The results obtained by using this failure criterion show that aging at 150°C under 1.7 bars oxygen (24h, 48h and 96h) leads to a significant reduction (about 27%) of the sample critical energy release rate. This reduction is not affected by the aging time and is possibly due to the material embrittlement induced by thermo-oxidation

on the external surface of pre-aged samples, independent of the aging time.

Using a failure criterion with constant G_c , the good agreement between experimental measurements and numerical calculations is obtained only for high crack density values. Han et al [10] and Hahn et al. [11] have shown an increase of the critical energy release rate with increasing crack density. Some authors (Ogi and Takao [12], Vinogradov and Hashin [13]) have also proposed probabilistic criteria to take into account this effect.

In this work, we propose a criterion of the form (Eq. 9):

$$G(\bar{\sigma}, d) = G_c(d) \quad (9)$$

in which $G_c(d)$ is the critical energy release rate as a function of the matrix crack density.

A possible expression of $G(d)$ is:

$$G_c(d) = G_{\min} + G_0(1 - \exp(-Rd)) \quad (10)$$

In which G_{\min} is the critical energy corresponding to the appearance of first crack; G_0 and R are parameters with less physical significance, to be identified. Tab. 1 presents the parameters of Eq. (10) identified for un-aged and pre-aged (24h, 48h, 96h) samples.

	Un-aged	Aged (24h, 48h, 96h)
G_{\min} (J/m^2)	237	209
G_0 (J/m^2)	196	122
R	2,3	2,3

Tab. 1. Parameters for $G(d)$ (Eq. 10) identified from the experimental points.

It can be noted that G_{\min} and G_0 are significantly affected by the aging process (11% for G_{\min} and 37% for G_0): R is the same for un-aged and pre-aged samples.

Fig. 6 shows a comparison between experimental measurements and numerical simulations carried out by employing Eq. (10). The experimental curves are now correctly simulated. There is a reduction of critical energy release rate in the pre-aged specimens compared to un-aged specimens.

Fig. 6: Experimental – numerical evolution of evolutions of crack density in function of applied stress (G_c varying with crack density)

3.2 Investigation about a possible link between the macroscopic (fibre/matrix) and the mesoscopic (ply) scale

Some research studies have shown that thermo oxidation induces matrix shrinkage and fiber/matrix debonding at the local scale [4]. In fact, thermo-oxidation induced shrinkage produces internal stresses which contribute to the total stress and may lead to the onset of damage. In matrix rich zones (low V_f) the amount of matrix shrinkage is large and the fiber/matrix debonding sites are usually more numerous. The extent of fiber/matrix debonding increases also with increasing aging time. It is interesting to study whether there is a link between the onset of fibre/matrix thermo-oxidation induced debonding and the faster development of matrix cracks at the ply scale for pre-aged samples, and the related reduction of critical energy release rate.

During tensile tests, the polished edges of the samples were registered by means of polymer replicas allowing microscopic observations of the cracked surfaces. **Fig. 7** presents SEM observations of the polymer replicas carried out on pre-aged specimens subjected to tensile loads.

Fig. 7: SEM observations of replicas registered on specimens aged under 1.7 bars oxygen and then subjected to tensile test.

Fig. 7a shows damage induced by thermo oxidation at the local scale (fibre/matrix debonding) and a matrix crack at the ply scale. We can observe that the ply crack is not associated with thermo-oxidation induced pre-damaged areas. **Fig. 7b** (tilted 45°) shows a matrix crack crossing the contours of the fibers in a zone of high V_f . This result shows that there is no clear link between thermo-oxidation induced damage at the local scale and matrix ply cracking. This enforces the hypothesis that the reduction of critical energy release rate in pre-aged samples is solely due to the material embrittlement induced by thermo-oxidation on the sample surfaces, independent of the aging time.

Conclusions

In this work, the effects of thermo oxidation on the matrix cracking of cross-ply [0/90]_s laminates were studied. The results show a significant reduction of matrix cracking critical energy release rate of pre-aged specimens compared to the non-aged ones. The cracking kinetics is identical for the pre-aged specimens. The reduction of the critical energy release rate in pre-aged specimens is related to the material degradation (embrittlement) of the surfaces exposed to the thermo oxidative environment, having an effect on the onset and the instantaneous propagation of the matrix cracks. On the other hand, SEM observations on replicas show that there is no direct link between thermo-oxidation induced damage at fiber/matrix scale and matrix cracking at the ply scale.

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank EADS IW (J. Cinquin) for providing the composite material used in this work.

References

1. Rouquie, S., et al., *Thermal cycling of carbon/epoxy laminates in neutral and oxidative environments*. Composites Science and Technology, 2005. **65**(3-4): p. 403-409.
2. Olivier, L., et al., *Characterization by ultra-micro indentation of an oxidized epoxy polymer: Correlation with the predictions of a kinetic model of oxidation*. Polymer Degradation and Stability, 2008. **93**(2): p. 489-497.
3. Olivier, L., et al., *Development of experimental, theoretical and numerical tools for studying thermo-oxidation of CFRP composites*. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 2009. **40**(8): p. 1008-1016.
4. Lafarie-Frenot, M.C., et al., *Thermo-oxidation behaviour of composite materials at high temperatures: A review of research activities carried out within the COMEDI program*. Polymer Degradation and Stability, 2010. **95**(6): p. 965-974.
5. Nairn, J.A. and D.A. Mendels, *On the use of planar shear-lag methods for stress-transfer analysis of multilayered composites*. Mechanics of Materials, 2001. **33**(6): p. 335-362.
6. Lee, J. and I. Daniel, *Progressive transverse cracking of cross-ply composite laminates*. Composites Science and Technology, 1990. **24**: p. 19.
7. Berthelot, J., et al., *Transverse cracking of cross-ply laminates: Part 1. Analysis*. Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing, 1996. **27A**: p. 13.
8. Nairn, J.A., *Fracture mechanics of composites with residual thermal stresses*. Journal of Applied Mechanics, 1997. **64**: p. 804-810.
9. Hashin, Z., *Finite thermoelastic fracture criterion with application to laminate cracking analysis*. Journal of the Mechanics and Physics of Solids, 1996. **44**: p. 1129.
10. Han, Y., H. Hahn, and R. Croman, *A simplified analysis of transverse ply cracking in cross-ply laminates*. Composites Science and Technology, 1988. **31**: p. 13.
11. Hahn, H., Y. Han, and R. Kim, *Resistance curves for ply cracking in composite laminates, in 33rd International SAMPE Symposium* 1988.
12. Ogi, K. and Y. Takao, *Modeling of time-dependent behaviour of deformation and transverse cracking in cross-ply laminates*. Advanced Composite Materials, 2001. **10**(1): p. 24.
13. Vinogradov, V. and Z. Hashin, *Probabilistic energy based model for prediction of transverse cracking in cross-ply laminates*. International Journal of Solids and Structures, 2005. **42**: p. 28.